

Senior Project

Smart Recycling Paper: An Entrepreneurship Project

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my mother for her unwavering support, encouragement, and love throughout this journey. Her guidance and belief in me have been a constant source of strength, inspiring me to persevere even in the face of challenges. Her sacrifices and dedication have shaped me into the person I am today, and for that, I am forever grateful. This project would not have been possible without her endless support, wisdom, and motivation.

1.1 Background

The recycling of paper is the process by which waste paper is converted into new paper products. This process offers numerous significant benefits beyond the preservation of trees. It is less energy- and water-intensive than paper production from wood pulp. Furthermore, it prevents waste paper from occupying landfills and generating methane as it decomposes. Approximately two-thirds of all paper products in the United States are currently recovered and recycled, although not all of this material is transformed into new paper. After repeated processing, the fibers become excessively short for the production of new paper. There are three categories of paper that can be utilized as feedstocks for manufacturing recycled paper: mill broke, pre-consumer waste, and post-consumer waste. Mill broke consists of paper trimmings and other paper scrap from the manufacturing process, and is recycled within the paper mill. Pre-consumer waste refers to material that has left the paper mill but was discarded prior to consumer use. Post-consumer waste encompasses material discarded after consumer use. The advantages of paper recycling include the conservation of energy, water, and landfill space. Additionally, paper recycling reduces greenhouse gas emissions, and the recycled fiber serves as a sustainable, cost-effective resource for the production of new paper products.

Information about business

1. Company Name

NGCO is a novel technology company that specializes in paper recycling, aiming to provide benefits to a wide range of stakeholders while focusing on environmental sustainability. The company's name, NGCO, is derived from "new generation company" and reflects its commitment to intelligent recycling practices that benefit organizations, corporations, and academic institutions. Each letter in the company name represents a specific concept. The 'N' signifies a new societal approach, promoting awareness of paper waste reduction and environmental conservation. The 'G' represents the future generation, who will inhabit a less polluted environment and gain a deeper understanding of paper recycling technologies. The letters "CO" denote the company itself, which will conduct paper recycling operations.

2. Company Slogan

Smart recycling.

Smart recycling is a slogan of our company which describe a smart ideas of recycling and reusing waste paper

3. Design Style

4. Colors

Green Color sign for renewal, nature, and energy that are associated with growth, harmony, and even freshness .green color is a natural choose in interior design as an ideal background or backup because we used to see everything green as a human. The red color sign for the part of recycling industries. The gray and black colors sign for timeless and practical activities associated with loss or depression. It also signs for strength of our business in the industry.

1.0 Executive Summary

1.1 Objectives

- Reduce the pollution surrounding air which has negative effect on our environmental and reducing greenhouse gas emissions which helps to protect biodiversity.
- Promote the economic activity by increasing export waste paper.
- Enhance the profitable re-using or recycling program for Government, Educational facilities, Business, Community and other Institutions.
- Reduce Government expenses by saving landfill space, wages, transportation, and other environmental issues.
- Enhance business organization by re-using paper and recycling it.
- Decrease the paper consumption.
- Strengthen employment opportunities.
- Enhance the recycling concept for sustainability.

1.2 Vision

To be the leading paper recycling company in the Middle East by providing innovative solutions focused on the needs and preferences of our customers. This also adds significant value to shareholders' equity with us.

1.3 Mission

The NGCO intends to become one of the leading manufacturers in the field of recycling in Republic of Yemen. Based on, its responsibility towards society and the homeland as a main target for the NGCO. The main objective is divided into three sub-targets:

Environmental Dimension: Reduce the pollution surrounding air which has negative effect on environment and reducing greenhouse gas emissions which helps to protect biodiversity.

Economic Dimension: Improve and growth both Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Gross Domestic Product (GDP) rate as a result.

Social Dimension: The recycling reduce consumption of natural resources, save money, reduce pollution and waste, and create jobs and boost the economy for community as a whole.

Chart: Highlights

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1.4 Keys to Success

- Innovative new technology products for re-using waste paper.
- Exclusive distribution rights to ground-breaking products not currently available in our market.
- Establishing the new production line for recycling waste paper and waste wood for convert it to raw materials for using.
- Create opportunities to export raw materials paper via recycling waste paper and waste wood to create paper lines trading which reflect improving economy.
- Enhance the recycling concept for other waste materials that could create a good opportunity to other investors for investing in waste other raw materials.
- Sustainability environment by reducing pollution in Yemen cause of burning waste papers.

2.0 Company Summary

2.1 Company Ownership

NGCO was established in 2018 by 6 members of founders. The company is a privately held-Corporation owned in total by its co-founders, Zakaria, Zaid, Kamal, Amr, and Hanan.

This includes having articles published in various newspapers or magazines as one of the most popular paper recycling in the city. All in all the proprietorship and the operation owned by our team members, and also our company will get the license from 'EPSON' to start to operate

2.3 Company Locations and Facilities

The NGCO location is Sana'a city in 70Street, the recycling facilities will be located on a 1776 square meter property owned by company founders. 222 meter will be set aside for the recycling facility set up and operation and the rest of the space will be for the management and inventories. This site is ideal as it provides access to other areas and streets. Also most of the institutions of Ngoc's target are near him.

Additionally, we did the center-of-gravity method because this method will be helping us to get the best location and reducing the cost of distribute of our product, so based on this method we chose the 70street as location of NGCO.

Location	Quantities soled per menthe		
70 ST	500	5.31	4.23
hawlan ST	200	5.33	4.18
70 ST	500	5.29	4.18
70 ST	300	5.31	4.20
70 ST New point	200	5.30	4.21

3.0 Products

3.1 Products and Production Description

Product DESCRIPTION

Epson paper lab a-8000

Epson paper lab a-8000 Paper-Lab is ideal for organizations that need to securely destroy confidential information as well as recycle paper in an environmentally friendly, eco-efficient and sustainable way.

Paper-Lab Features

1. Dry Fibre technology

Defibration

A defibration unit developed by Epson mechanically breaks down used paper into long, thin fibres without using water. All traces of information are completely and securely destroyed instantaneously.

Binding

The fibres from the used paper are binded together using a binding material. This material is available in a number of different colors to allow Paper-Lab users to produce paper in an array of colors or to increase paper whiteness.

Forming

Pressure is applied to the binded fibres to form new sheets of paper. Paper-Lab users can produce A4- and A3-sized sheets in various thicknesses by setting controls for paper density, thickness, and shape.

2. Enhanced security

Paper-Lab enhances information security by completely destroying confidential documents. Instead of being transported off-site by a contractor, waste paper is reduced to fine fibres on site. Unlike paper that has been run through a shredder, the fibres carry no discernible information whatsoever. Paper-Lab is therefore an ideal solution for local government offices and other institutions that handle large volumes of confidential documents. It protects personal data while giving institutions, residents, and customer peace of mind.

3. Fast production of various types of paper

Paper-Lab produces the first new sheet of paper in about three minutes of having loaded it with waste paper and pressing the Start button. It can produce about 720 sheets of A4 paper per hour. By up cycling used paper into paper that has higher value, such as copier paper, cardstock for business cards, or colored paper for handbills, companies and local governments can produce whatever kind of new paper products they want, whenever they need them.

4. Lower environmental impacts

Paper-Lab creates paper in a waterless papermaking process. Ordinarily it takes about a cup of water to make a single A4 sheet of paper. Given that water is a precious global resource, Epson felt a dry process was needed.

Note: A small amount of water is used to maintain a certain level of humidity inside the system.

1. Paper-Lab is the first in-office papermaking system to use a dry process, according to Seiko Epson's global research as of November 2016.
2. The system can use ordinary A3- and A4-sized copy paper as raw material.
3. A small amount of water is used to maintain a certain level of humidity inside the

e-Studio306LP + e-Studio RD30

Speeds & Feeds

- Up to 30 pages per minute (letter)
- Up to 5 paper sources including bypass with a maximum capacity of 3,200 sheets.

- Feeds up to 110 lbs through the bypass.
- Standard Copy, Print, and Colour Scan.
- Maximum duty cycle : 120,000 impressions per month.
- 100 %Toner recycle system.
- Copy and Print, then erase paper and re-use again.

Us & Them

- Copy/Print resolution up to 2400 x 600 dpi.
- 1GB of Memory along with 160GB Hard disk for document processing and storage.
- 100 sheet capacity reversing automatic document feeder option.
- Up to 12,060 user templates to provide ease of one touch operation.
- Up to 200 storage boxes for document storage within the device.

Security & Connectivity

- User authentication along with Role Based Access Control allows administrators to determine which function individual users can access.
- Supports Windows 2000/XP/Win7/Win8/2003/Vista/2008, Mac X, Linux, UNIX, CUPS.
- Connectivity to 10BaseT/100BaseTX Ethernet, Wireless LAN 802.11b/g, USB 2.0, Bluetooth (HCRP)
- Top Access web interface for status monitoring and remote configuration is included.
- PCL 6, PostScript 3 and XPS print drivers included – no additional charge for Post-Script!
- Common Criteria and EAL3 certified.
- Standard SED (Self-Encrypting HDD).
- Standard hard disk encryption and data overwrite.

Reduce & Save

- Environmental choice certified, reducing energy cost.
- Standard duplex allows two sided copying, reducing paper and saving paper cost.
- N-up copies allow up to 8 pages to be copied on a single sheet, reducing storage space and increasing savings.
- Access codes - monitors and restrict usage based on pre-defined limits, reducing misuse and increasing savings.

Better & Faster

- First copy out time of less than 4.7 seconds, allows quicker copies and reduces wait time.
- Advance job reservation – It is now possible to pre-scan up to 10 jobs while another job is being processed, saving time.
- Job build – conveniently combine different copy jobs in one seamless step, save time by removing unnecessary steps.
- Send and receive faxes at the same time through the two line fax option saving time.
- Templates to store and quickly recall commonly used jobs, saving time by one touch activation of such jobs.

Efficiency & Productivity

- Automatic magnification ratio – scales a page to best fit the sheet size of media in the input tray.
- Automatic paper selection – Selects the right paper from available paper source, based on the original paper size.
- Advanced Scanning Option – Able to scan into Microsoft Word®, Excel® or Searchable PDF automatically!
- Annotation / Page numbering – Allows date and/or page numbers to be added to the copy output.

- Cover Sheet insertion – Allows insertion of front and back pages of the document from a different paper source.
- Booklet function - Automatically print pages in the correct order so the document can be folded and stapled to form a booklet.

Erase Units

- 30 PPM Single Pass Duplexing.
- Scan to network folder and Erase at 15 PPM.
- One paper cassette for erased paper.
- One paper cassette for non-erased paper.
- Letter size maximum.

Production DESCRIPTION

Paper Making Machine

A4 Paper Making Machine

The NGCO will *A4 Paper Making Machine* to produce raw materials from waste paper and waste wood that output could exported to others paper manufacturing.

The *A4 Paper Making Machine* will produce output of paper style: A4 paper, printing paper, copying paper and writing the output paper weight: 60-80g/m², its input from using raw material: waste paper, wood pulp as input. The machine capacity: 5~15Tons per day, and its working speed: 150-120m/min. The Power 50~132 KW.

Automatic A4 paper cutting and wrapping machine

Machine Description

Automatic A4 paper cutting and wrapping machine is A4 copy cut size sheeting and wrapping machine that suits for small capacity production or for the starter. This machine is featured by.

- Type: paper cutting and wrapping
- High speed: max 300m/min
- Low production capacity: 4-5 reams/min
- Small space required: 7m*7m
- Easy operation

- Less labor power: only 3 men required
- Low cost

3.2 Sourcing

The NGCO will purchase "Product" directly from manufacturers and purchases "Resources" from local partners as showed in market segmentation analysis. Also, the NGCO will export the output of manufacturing to other manufactured.

The NGCO expected to operate on a 30-35% profit margin for its production line, and expected to operate on a 10 - 15 % profit margin for its products selling.

To further reduce costs, the NGCO sets its strategy to increase production as its possible to reduce the operating cost.

3.3 Future Products

When it comes to paper communications, recycled paper is the greenest option, it uses less energy, water, and produces lower carbon emissions than the manufacturing of non-recycled paper and at the same time reduces the amount of waste to landfill – as paper can be recycled 4 to 5 times. With advances in technology and processes, recycled paper is now as white and has the same print performance as non-recycled paper. For many years, individual consumers, industries and governments have all purchased printing and writing paper made with a high recycled-fiber content.

Why? Because they believe it is the most responsible and environmentally friendly thing to do. But is it really better for the environment?

Traditionally, fiber for paper and paper packaging comes from the wood of trees, with other sources of fiber – such as sugarcane and straw – making a minor contribution. In more recent times, waste paper has also been used as a source of fibers. These recycled fibers are processed to make paper products similar to those made from original wood fibers.

When papers are recycled, it is used to help manufacture new products. There are many different uses for recycled paper, and the products made from recycled paper actually cost about

the same as those made from other resources. You can do your part for the environment by purchasing recycled goods, and you won't be spending much, if any, extra money to do so. What are some of the products made from recycled paper? Our company will have other machines to produce some other products that are related to paper after recycling. Here are some of the products that made from paper recycled

- **Paper Towels and Napkins.** Recycling confidential documents can become a paper napkin to be usage.

- **Cardboard.** This handy material is used to package many different items, including cereal, pizza and your latest online order. And yes, cardboard is made with recycled office paper.

- **Magazines and Newspapers.** Many of these reading materials are printed on recycled paper. Not sure if your daily newspaper is using recycled materials? Give them a call! And make sure to throw that newspaper into the recycling bin when you're finished with it.

- **Paper bags.**

Paper bags can be recycled with other paper items, making them as easy to recycle

- **Note books**

Spiral notebooks are a great tool for everyone from college students to busy professionals. A loose-leaf notebook is a necessity for students everywhere, and no lawyer could imagine life without a yellow legal pad. The company will provide a machine to produce note books to be useful and helpful in everybody's life.

- **Recyclable cubs**

The most important product we will produce from recycled paper is recyclable cups that contains 95% paper and 5% plastic and will be made with different shapes and types.

4.0 Market Analysis Summary

4.1 Market Segmentation

Market segmentation is the process of dividing a market of potential customers into groups, or segments, based on different characteristics as Geography, Demography, Behavioral or Psychograph. NGCO was divided its customers into two segments which are demography and geography. Both segments are satisfying the company's strategy. First segment, is demography which focus on many of sectors such as education sector, banks sectors, newspaper & magazines, and printing press. Each sector, divided into two segments such as the large number of sector and the sector's kind. Second segment, is geography which focus on the location for each sector as whole and focus on distances between sectors.

Table: Market Analysis

Market Segmentation				
Segment	No. Sectors	No.	Expectation of paper usage (gm)	Total paper usage (gm)
Education Sectors	380	520,769	1,600	833,230,400
Government Sectors	230		2,300	529,000
Banks & Financial Sectors	53	-	27,480	1,456,440
Printing Press Sectors	65	-	835,850	54,330,250
Others	150	-	1,500	225,000
Total No.	878	520,769	868,730	889,771,090

Chart: Market Analysis (Pie)

4.2 Target Market Segment Strategy

A company cannot concentrate on all the segments of the market in short-run strategy. The beginning target for NGCO is focusing on the large number of those sectors for recycling waste paper and export it. At the same time, we focus on main strategy is re-using waste paper by using the new technology which will satisfy our customers from decreasing the waste paper and spend on them. On other side, there are many of directions to target market segment strategy which includes market trends, market growth, and market need.

4.2.1 Market Trends

The re-using and recycling paper is ideal in Yemeni's market especially. There are reasons behind, first reason is Yemeni's market consume a lot of waste paper without any recycling or re-using for waste paper which has effect both environment and economy as a result of these consumption. The New Generation strategy comes by its responsibilities towards both environmental and economic. The following facts were listed by estimation result.

- The Yemeni's market consume more than 1000 Tons of paper per year.
- The Yemeni's market spend more than 4 million dollar for papers.

- Reduce of the air pollution resulting in 1 Tons of burned paper equivalent 24 kg of air pollutants which reflect.
- Reanimation the economy activities by promote recycling paper which doesn't exist in the Yemeni's market.
- Reduce the CPI which used as a measure of inflation, and enhance the export's balance for the country.

4.2.2 Market Growth

According to figures for 2015, global paper consumption has reached 398 million tons per year—which worked out to 12,620 kg per second in 2013! Also in 2015, global demand for paper and cardboard increased by an average of 2.2%.

Graphic paper and packing paper represent approximately 88% of consumption. Based on high growth and absence of competitions inside Yemeni market, which make the Ngco has an opportunity to capture market- before more competitors enter.

MARKET ATTRACTIVENESS

1. Strategic Value:

The Yemeni market is a strategic, and available, segment for the NGCO. The reason is absence the competitions in re-using and recycling paper field which make us to have competitive advantages by creating strong relation with government and organizational to related. The New Generation will attempt to capture this partnership as a value to its strategy.

2. Market Size:

The size of the Yemeni market is an important factor. While the large number of paper consumption increases each year will make it difficult to gain significant share of the market in the near term, it does help to ensure that there will be customers available to the NGCO such as education and business sectors.

3. Potential for Profit:

The potential for profit in this segment is good enough to develop and extend the company increase the profits. The operating costs required to address this segment are minimal after established, allowing a majority of service revenue to be turned directly into profit.

4.2.3 Market Needs

Within the Yemeni's market, there are a number of segments, each with distinct objectives,

resources, and needs

4.3 Industry Analysis

The NGCO is poised to take advantage of the trends identified above. By enhance the marketing and management experience, small business focus, and local presence in key markets, the NGCO will help to growing number of re-using and recycling paper which increase their chances for success

The NGCO is a Limited Liability Company designed to offer limited liability. NGCO will initially focus its operations on how to use the new technology for re-using paper and how it could recycling paper as the main object. The NGCO can focus on its strategy to target its client base to encompass other regions through the use of existing technology.

4.3.2 Competition and Buying Patterns

4.3.2 .1 Competitors to NGCO fall into two categories:

1. Segment Rivals: Yemeni Market lacks these rivals in this time from any market segments above. NGCO expect onset competition with many competitors as long as the re-using and recycling concept spread. NGCO will attempt to ensure its competition advantages in all its target market.

2. Market Rivals: There is a number of available Market Rivals who compete in a track of recycling different types of metal, oil, and plastic except paper recycling is almost uncompetitive. NGCO expects competition from those who compete in recycling factories. NGCO sets a good strategy to deal with all variable factors.

4.3.2.2 NGCO describe both Buyer and Seller patterns as a consumer behavior falls into two categories: Culture Factor, and Social Factor.

Culture Factor: Culture factor refer to purchasing power for the Yemeni market, such as at the beginning of each academic year for education sector, the purchasing power for Culture Factor could effecting by three types of factors: culture, subculture, and social class.

Social Factor: Social Factor purchasing power dependent on four PEST analysis which describe Political, Economic, Technological, and SOICO Culture.

4.3.3 Industry Participants

In principle, the competition in re-using and recycling paper is almost nonexistent. Potential competition will comes from the competitors of recycling companies. Due to the size of the available market, it will be exceptionally difficult for any of these competitors to gain significant market share. However, it will also be difficult for the NGCO to control the market.

5.0 Strategy and Implementation Summary

Implementation summary

NGCO's strategy is to leverage its existing advantages of location, established new clientele, and reputation; and combined all of these to create a value added product/service experience to its new customers and to enhance appeal to New Generation's. In short, the company seeks to create a value-added approach to its new paper establishment and bring in new customers to achieve both a higher margin than previously experienced and increase overall profitability through new customers.

5.2 Value Proposition

The profit related to the project is showed here in two points:

First: presenting the value for the private and public sectors:

We are making an effective service in saving costs and budgets and it considered as an effective way to eliminate the problem of the garbage that increases each day and causes environmental issues which also increases pollution. This service will help to eliminate the difficulty of getting rid of it and save a clean and clear environment with less cost and suitable price.

Second: presenting the value to individuals.

The service we are presenting now is processed in recycling the available products we have which is saving dollars and it saves employment opportunities and also reduces unjust consumption for the directly surrounded environment, which effect directly on human beings, animal and earth. Furthermore, it saves for the consumers financial returning when they sell these products which we can recycle and from all these sides we emerge the importance of the project for individual people.

5.3 Competitive Edge

Paper recycling:-

Is a process of recycling the waste paper which is collected from schools and organizations and then sent to the paper factory which recycle it and sell it inside country or outside, near Arabic markets and this of course provides the difficult process by reducing the rate of paper consumption in addition to the provision of quantities The paper needed by the market in record time.

The recycling process:-

To recycle paper, many steps should be followed to produce a useful product

- 1- **Collection:** recycling begins with collecting paper from authorities, other organization.
- 2- **Sorting:** after collection, sorting is the most important step of paper recycling to produce a good quality of paper we need a good sorting.
- 3- **Shredding:** paper is shredded into thin slices by the shredding machine.
- 4- **Washing and floating:** after shredding, paper floated into water tanks.
- 5- **Mixing or blending:** the floated paper then mixed by a mixing machine to create the pulp.
- 6- **Paper forming:** paper is formed into different shapes according to what is needed.
- 7- **Drying:** formed paper should be dried.

Benefits of paper recycling:-

Economically:

- 1- It helps to reduce the importing of the raw materials, which is important to the paper industry.
- 2- Job creation: it offers excellent opportunities for unemployed.
- 3- It saves energy.

Environmentally:

- 1- Helps to get rid of the waste paper by a process which protects the environment and avoiding pollution which can come of burning paper.
- 2- Reduce demand for wood and fiber and allow the forest to increase its ability to absorb carbon in the atmosphere.
- 3- Protecting the agriculture lands.

According to the environment protection agency in USA, producing one ton of paper saves 4100 kilowatt of energy in an hour and saves 28cubic meter of water. It also reduces air pollution by 24 kg of air pollution.

Culturally:

Since paper recycling is a new concept for a lot of people and few only know it, community awareness of this concept will help a lot of people.

The benefits that the government gets of paper selling:-

- 1- Reducing the expenses of waste disposal and transportation.
- 2- Reducing the spread of diseases and environmental pollution.
- 3- Reducing the number of workers.
- 4- Increasing the economics of the country.

5.4 Marketing Strategy

The Company has chosen to focus on the production of the papers and recycling post-consumer. Because of the industry experience and expertise of the management we have identified a significant available market in the Sana'a. All of our initial marketing strategy will be to secure contracts in that segment, and after reaching full planned capacity, look to grow in concert with that segment and related markets. We see little need at present for further market research and development, and will focus on continually updating our production technology in an effort to remain in the forefront of our chosen marketplace. Because NGCO has a unique technology and experience of NGCO Management in the Company's chosen industry segment, NGCO is able to identify all of the potential customers for each of the products we will produce in our facility. While most of the production of paper is ultimately intended to be used internally.

Promotion Strategy and Marketing Programs:

NGCO promotional strategy will be two-fold: first phase promotion will focus on before, during, and six months following our opening; the second phase of promotion will deal with the long term. The purpose of the first phase is to assist with rapid market entry to ensure early and sustained profitability. The purpose of the second phase is to ensure long-term growth and help propel us toward achieving our goal of expanding state wide and sales line of NGCO.

The strategies will be implements through the following marketing tactics and programs:

First Phase Promotions:

❖ Publicity:

We will send news releases to all of the major newspapers in Yemen. Publication of news articles about Mid-Atlantic Recycling will lend great credibility and be an excellent way

to let all target markets know about this new, innovative business and the solutions it provides for municipalities and users of papers. We will similarly seek publicity in the form of news stories from local radio and television stations.

❖ **Advertising:**

We will utilize direct mail and face-to-face promotional strategies to raise awareness about our products and services in the target markets. Newspaper advertising may also be used. Radio and television ads are not certain; we will evaluate their effectiveness before further implementation.

❖ **Internet:**

We will have a content heavy website geared toward educating potential customers about the benefits of our products and services. All literature, business cards, etc. will include our website and e-mail address information.

Second Phase Promotions:

➤ **Publicity:**

As the business grows and expands we will continue to seek publicity through news media to tout our successes.

➤ **Advertising:**

We will continue to make face-to-face contact with customers and potential customers. Mail-outs will be done again within a few months of start-up. The second round of mail

outs will be updated to reflect the benefits provided to customers thus far. Such mail-outs will be sent periodically.

➤ **Internet:**

We will continue to have a comprehensive website. The website will be updated to provide responses to frequently asked questions. After the first six months, and certainly after the first year, we will evaluate the viability of having target clients advertise on our site, and conversely, we will evaluate viability of advertising on our target client's websites (if applicable) .

5.4.1 Promotion Strategy

Relationships are the key to success in the distribution business. Personal selling will remain our most important means of promotion. It needs skill and experience in sales, distribution and skills in customer service and relations. In addition to personal selling, The NGCO has identified several other means of advertising and publicity. The company will send news releases to local media and press, as well as trade magazines to try to get product and company feature coverage in front of the eyes of our customers - as well as the end consumer. We will also produce a few generic press releases about the products we are distributing for our customers to use toward healthy environment and publicity coverage for their businesses in local publications. Third, we shall have a monthly newsletter for current of potential customers. This newsletter will highlight new and current trends in the industry, upcoming conventions and trade shows, offer promotions and special deals, as well as provide new recipes, fun tips and other information that can be used in their business. We will also highlight not just our products, but also display ideas and success stories of other business in the industry.

5.4.2 Distribution Strategy

The primary distribution function is to deliver the goods to the end consumer as efficiently and effectively as possible and to carry out this task the distribution component which represents one of the elements of the marketing mix.

The basic distribution depends on a group of important elements that combine with each other goods displayed and which are represented in **four elements**:

- 1- Distribution.
- 2- Promotion.
- 3- Pricing.
- 4- Resources, institutional potential and production cost.

Distribution Functions:-

- 1- Delivery of goods and brands to the target consumers at the right time and place.
- 2- Provide consumers with all information and data of goods and to show how to use and maintain them.
- 3- Ensure the transfer of goods and brands by appropriate means.
- 4- Store goods, raw materials and semi-finished items until needed.
- 5- Financial facilities and insurance and related transactions of freight and insurance on the goods from their production centers to place of consumption.

5.4.4 Pricing Strategy

Pricing of our product must remain initially competitive with our rivals. Management does however plan to price our recycled papers somewhat more than our other products to reflect production costs. This is typical within the industry and can create higher margins. If our company is able to capture a significant number of newer customers, then management will consider a rise in overall prices to reflect our established unique position. Paper recycled will be competitively priced in relation to the dictates of the market. The pricing fits with the general positioning of paper recycled as providing high-level quality expertise.

We intend our income structure to match our cost structure, so as to ensure that the salaries/consultants fees we pay to assure good reports and service are balanced by the fee we charge. We will make sure that we charge for the service, workmanship with our aim being to achieve a gross profit margin of at least 50%. Naturally services targeted at the market will have higher mark ups as these clients are less price sensitive. All in all we intend our prices to be extremely competitive on the market. With time and as we become known on the market we foresee an increase in our consultancy fee -- tempered by market dictates. Market research reports should be competitively priced which will, of course, require that reports be very well planned, focusing on very important topics, and well presented.

5.5 Sales Strategy

The Sales Forecast table shows net after cost of goods sold monthly. This is due to the variability of what comprises an "upgrade" kit. To account this variability, we assume that all sales will cover the cost of goods and shipping/handling, plus a minimum of \$50 revenue to Brilliant Points. Note that all company expenses other than cost of goods are accounted for against this revenue stream. The only "hidden" variable is the cost of goods sold which will be bundled into the price of the upgrade kits. We expect sales to ramp up from zero to a total of approximately \$5,000 sold the first year. In the second year, sales are expected to increase to approximately \$9,000, and in the third year to approximately \$13,000. We expect sales to plateau and begin to fall, perhaps significantly after the fourth year, as licensing penetration increases. Licensing revenues are not expected to be realized until the second year of operations. We project reaching 1.5 percent penetration of the potential presentation seat market by end of second year of operations, with 2.5 percent penetration by end of third year. We expect licensing penetration to continue to increase year over year through the duration of the patent protection (15 years). It is expected that we will achieve at least 50 percent penetration of this market before the patent expires. Sales forecasts will be impacted by overall economy, as well as schools and universities we are dealing with. Preliminary few tests have shown extremely favorable response, so we do not anticipate any significant negative response. While the forecast presentation market growth may not materialize, the installed base will still need to upgrade and/or replace failed equipment, providing on-going revenue even if this should occur.

5.5.1 Sales Forecast

Chart: Sales by Months

Chart: Sales by Year

Table: Sales Forecast

Sales By Monthly				
2018	Sales Machines	Product A4	Product A3	After sales service & Other
Jan	\$ 1,000	\$ 62,400	\$ 79,800	\$ 500
Feb	\$ 1,010	\$ 62,400	\$ 79,800	\$ 550
Mar	\$ 1,020	\$ 62,400	\$ 79,800	\$ 605
Apr	\$ 1,030	\$ 68,640	\$ 87,780	\$ 666
May	\$ 1,041	\$ 68,640	\$ 87,780	\$ 732
Jun	\$ 1,051	\$ 68,640	\$ 87,780	\$ 805
Jul	\$ 1,062	\$ 75,504	\$ 96,558	\$ 886
Aug	\$ 1,072	\$ 75,504	\$ 96,558	\$ 974
Sep	\$ 1,083	\$ 75,504	\$ 96,558	\$ 1,072
Oct	\$ 1,094	\$ 83,054	\$ 106,214	\$ 1,179
Nov	\$ 1,105	\$ 83,054	\$ 106,214	\$ 1,297
Dec	\$ 1,116	\$ 83,054	\$ 106,214	\$ 1,427
Sales By Yearly				
Yealy	Sales Machines	Product A4	Product A3	After sales service & Other
2018	\$ 12,683	\$ 868,795	\$ 1,111,055	\$ 10,692
2019	\$ 13,951	\$ 955,675	\$ 1,222,161	\$ 11,761
2020	\$ 15,346	\$ 1,051,242	\$ 1,344,377	\$ 12,937

5.6 Milestones

Table: Milestones

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Charts: Milestones

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6.0 Management Summary

CEO is the mind behind Paper Recycling Technologies. He saw the need for paper to be recycle and use it again. With the development, determination, motivation, and persistence of everyone involved, NGCO will be the leading producer of recycled paper in the future.

The management team believes that unique way of recycling will be change the way of consumer's overall by using recycling technologies. The responsibilities and duties of the management team are very important to reach its target. will be managed by the two founding partners, whose individual areas of expertise cover many of the functional aspects of the business.

6.1 Management Team

The responsibilities involved in the NGCO Recycling are great and abundant. NGCO Recycling's main purpose is to appeal to schools, university, and other companies by offering for waste paper disposal alternative, and to who environmentally conscious minded consumers by developing products that include recycled waste papers. Each executive member will have several responsibilities that are imperative to fulfill the duties in producing such unique products.

Mr. Zakaria Al-Kindi (CFO):

As founder and president of NGCO. Mr. Alkindi holed a Bachelor's degree from the Lebanese International University in International Business Management, he has an enough history of experience in distribution management, operation management, and financial management. Some of his duties will include overseeing the areas held by the other company executives, as well as the output produced by other employees. He will be in charge of the company's public relations. He will also have the job of hiring dedicated people and ensuring employees put their best efforts into the production of NGCO products. He will have the lead role in making decisions that concern the well being of NGCO.

(CEO) duties and responsibilities

- Develop high-quality business strategies and plans
- Ensure strategy alignment with objectives
- Lead with an example and motivate subordinates
- Encourage employee engagement
- Train a high performing managerial team
- Oversee all operations and business activities
- Make high-quality investing decisions
- Provide inspired leadership company wide.
- Enforce adherence to legal guidelines and in-house policies
- Ensure the company's complicity with legal and business ethics
- Review financial and non-financial reports
- Give advice for improvement and suggestions for solution
- Develop the company's culture and overall company vision
- Build trusting relations with key partners and stakeholders
- Work with senior stakeholders, chief financial officer, chief information officer, and other executives.
- Maintain contact with important shareholders
- Act as the primary spokesperson for the company.
- Train, motivate and lead others
- Analyze problematic situations and suggest solutions
- Keep abreast of the markets and industry trends

Mr. Kamal Al Sharafi (CFO):

As founder and president of NGCO. Mr. Al Sharafi holed a Bachelor's degree from the Lebanese International University in International Business Management, he has an enough history of experience in distribution management, and financial management. He is accountable for the administrative, financial, and risk management operations of the company, to include the development of a financial and operational strategy, metrics tied to that strategy, and the

ongoing development and monitoring of control systems designed to preserve company assets and report accurate financial results. Principal accountabilities are:

Planning

1. Assist in formulating the company's future direction and supporting tactical initiatives
2. Monitor and direct the implementation of strategic business plans
3. Develop financial and tax strategies
4. Manage the capital request and budgeting processes
5. Develop performance measures that support the company's strategic direction

Operations

1. Participate in key decisions as a member of the executive management team
2. Maintain in-depth relations with all members of the management team
3. Manage the accounting, human resources, investor relations, legal, tax, and treasury departments
4. Oversee the financial operations of subsidiary companies and foreign operations
5. Manage any third parties to which accounting or finance functions have been outsourced
6. Oversee the company's transaction processing systems
7. Implement operational best practices
8. Oversee employee benefit plans, with particular emphasis on maximizing a cost-effective benefits package
9. Supervise acquisition {[HYPERLINK "https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/4/acquisition-due-diligence-checklist"](https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/4/acquisition-due-diligence-checklist)} and negotiate acquisitions

Financial Information

1. Oversee the issuance of financial information
2. Personally review and approve all {HYPERLINK "https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/10/form-8-k"}, {HYPERLINK "https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/10/form-10-k"}, and {HYPERLINK "https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/10/form-10-q"} filings with the {HYPERLINK "https://www.accountingtools.com/articles/2017/5/16/securities-and-exchange-commission"} (if the company is publicly held)
3. Report financial results to the board of directors

Risk Management

1. Understand and mitigate key elements of the company's risk profile
2. Monitor all open legal issues involving the company, and legal issues affecting the industry
3. Construct and monitor reliable control systems
4. Maintain appropriate insurance coverage
5. Ensure that the company complies with all legal and regulatory requirements
6. Ensure that record keeping meets the requirements of auditors and government agencies
7. Report risk issues to the audit committee of the board of directors
8. Maintain relations with external auditors and investigate their findings and recommendations

Funding

1. Monitor cash balances and cash forecasts
2. Arrange for debt and equity financing
3. Invest funds
4. Invest pension funds

Mr. Amr Esam (CMO):

As founder and president of NGCO. Mr. Amr holed a Bachelor's degree from the Lebanese International University in International Business Management, he has an enough history of experience in distribution management, operation management. Some of his duties will include overseeing the planning, development and execution of an organization's marketing and advertising initiatives. Reporting directly to the chief executive officer, the CMO's primary responsibility is to generate revenue by increasing sales through successful marketing for the entire organization, using market research, pricing, product marketing, marketing communications, advertising and public relations. However, his responsible includes sales management, new business development, product development, distribution channel management and customer service. The CMO ensures the organization's message is distributed across channels and to targeted audiences in order to meet sales objectives.

As a senior-level marketing professional, a Chief Marketing Officer must be both analytical and creative, and possess extensive knowledge in a variety of disciplines such as production, information technology, legal and finance. CMOs often plan, direct and coordinate marketing budgets in accordance to organizational goals.

(CMO) duties and responsibilities

- "Listen" to the trends of the market and direct the market research efforts of the company
- Liaise with other departments to guide a unified approach to customer service, distribution etc. that meets market demands
- Define marketing strategies to support the company's overall strategies and objectives
- Develop a feasible marketing plan for the department and oversee its day-to-day implementation
- Plan and organize marketing functions and operations (product development, branding, communications etc.), and ensure they project the company's unique "voice"
- Design and coordinate promotional campaigns, PR and other marketing efforts across channels (digital, press etc.)
- Build a highly efficient team of marketing professionals
- Create a solid network of strategic partnerships

Ms. Hanan Al-Ogail (COO):

As founder and president of NGCO. Ms. Al-Ogail holed a Bachelor's degree from the Lebanese International University in International Business Management, she has an enough history of experience in distribution management, and operation management. Her job will be crucial in the growth of NGCO. She will ensure that day-to-day operations are conducted such that materials are received, methods and processes are standardized, and production is maximized to ensure uniform production of compost materials.

(COO) duties and responsibilities

- Design and implement business strategies, plans and procedures
- Set comprehensive goals for performance and growth
- Establish policies that promote company culture and vision
- Oversee daily operations of the company and the work of executives (IT, Marketing, Sales, Finance etc.)
- Lead employees to encourage maximum performance and dedication
- Evaluate performance by analyzing and interpreting data and metrics
- Write and submit reports to the CEO in all matters of importance
- Assist CEO in fundraising ventures
- Participate in expansion activities (investments, acquisitions, corporate alliances etc.)
- Manage relationships with partners/vendors

Mr. Zaid Musleh (CPO):

As founder and president of NGCO. Mr. Musleh holed a Bachelor's degree from the Lebanese International University in International Business Management, she has an enough history of experience in distribution management, and operation management. Her job will be

crucial in the growth of NGCO. She will ensure that day-to-day operations are conducted such that materials are received, methods and processes are standardized, and production is maximized to ensure uniform production of compost materials.

(CPO) duties and responsibilities

- In partnership with the executive team, identify opportunities and risks for delivering the company's services as a web-based business, including identification of competitive services, opportunities for innovation, and assessment of marketplace obstacles and technical hurdles to the business success.
- Identify technology trends and evolving social behavior that may support or impede the success of the business.
- Evaluate and identify appropriate technology platforms (including web application frameworks and the deployment stack) for delivering the company's services.
- Lead strategic planning to achieve business goals by identifying and prioritizing development initiatives and setting timetables for the evaluation, development, and deployment of all web based services.
- Participate as a member of the senior management team in establishing governance processes of direction and control to ensure that objectives are achieved, risks are managed appropriately and the organization's resources are used responsibly, particularly in the areas of software development, office networks and computers, and telecommunications.
- Establish a governance process that meets government, regulator, partner, and company expectations for customer information privacy.
- Direct development and execution of an company-wide information security and disaster recovery and business continuity plan.
- Communicate the company's technology strategy to investors, management, staff, partners, customers, and stakeholders.

Management Structures

1- Customer & Suppliers Relationship

Client Relations Manager job description

This Client Relations Manager job description template is optimized for posting to online job boards or careers pages and easy to customize for your company. **Client Relations**

Manager Responsibilities

Include:

- Building long-term relationships with key clients.
- Addressing customer concerns and complaints.
- Creating sales plans to generate revenue.

Responsibilities

- Build relationships with key employees among customers
- Create plans to address clients' business needs
- Advise clients on creating profitable processes
- Schedule regular meetings with customers to ensure they are satisfied
- Act as point of contact for complaints and escalate issues as appropriate
- Help sales team up-sell or cross-sell services and products
- Ensure both the company and clients adhere to contract terms
- Study competition to find new ways to retain customers
- Set sales and revenue targets and work diligently to meet them
- Collaborate with internal teams (e.g. sales, engineers, senior management) to address customers' needs

Supplier Relationship

Chamois seeks a supplier relationship manager to support our Procurement and Supply Management project. Procurement and Supply Management (PSM) is a five-year, multi-billion dollar project funded by United States Agency for International Development (USAID) that will consolidate the procurement and assistance components of the current USAID DELIVER and

USAID Supply Chain Management Systems (SCMS) programs. The project will be the primary vehicle through which USAID will procure and provide health

Responsibilities :

- Enhances supplier relationships by developing and continually improving upon post-award supplier processes
- Develops and drives supplier scorecards and ongoing supplier performance improvement working with supply base
- Promotes coordination of health commodity supply chain activities between partners through existing mechanisms and establishment of new forums as needed
- Provides technical guidance to key stakeholders working within the supply chain
- Promotes and monitors the implementation of an integrated supply chain involving key supply chain stakeholders at all levels of the system
- Offers input regarding negotiation processes and related tools
- Supports the development of supplier strategies, bid packages, and contracts
- Provides short term technical assistance and/or capacity building to field offices, as necessary
- Other duties as required

2- Marketing

Basic Job Description:

Determine the demand for products and services offered by a firm and its competitors and identify potential customers. Develop pricing strategies with the goal of maximizing the firm's profits or share of the market while ensuring the firm's customers are satisfied. Oversee product development or monitor trends that indicate the need for new products and services.

3- R & D

- A research and development (R&D) manager performs a number of highly important roles within an organization. They are responsible for research, planning, and implementing new programs and protocols into their company or organization and overseeing the development of new products. The industry in which a research and development manager works will likely have an impact on their specific duties, as these professionals often find employment in fields like healthcare, technology, business, and pharmaceuticals. The types of products produced by a pharmaceutical company are likely to be different from those produced by a technical company, so R&D managers have the ability to specialize according to their interests.
- Regardless of the specific field, R&D managers are usually responsible for overseeing the entire development process of new products and programs within an organization, from the initial planning phase to implementation or production. You will need to keep track of all the costs related to the creation of these new products and decide what ideas are worth pursuing. The R&D manager should also stay informed on what is happening in the research and development field at large in order to make sure their company is up-to-date and current with the most advanced R&D developments. As a manager, you will also have important managerial and administrative responsibilities and may be in charge of overseeing employees.

4- Sales manager

- Achieving growth and hitting sales targets by successfully managing the sales team.
- Designing and implementing a strategic sales plan that expands company's customer base and ensure it's strong presence.
- Managing recruiting, objectives setting, coaching and performance monitoring of sales representatives .

5- Storekeeper

Duties and Responsibilities

- Maintain receipts, records, and withdrawals of the stockroom
- Receive, unload, and shelve supplies

- Perform other stock-related duties, including returning, packing, pricing, and labeling supplies
- Inspect deliveries for damage or discrepancies and report those to accounting for reimbursements and record keeping
- Rotate stock and coordinate the disposal of surpluses
- Ensure adequate record keeping and manage all documentation to confirm proper stock levels and maintain inventory control
- Coordinate the handling of freight, the movement of equipment, and necessary minor repairs

6- Accounting

Accountant Job Duties:

- Prepares asset, liability, and capital account entries by compiling and analyzing account information.
- Documents financial transactions by entering account information.
- Recommends financial actions by analyzing accounting options.
- Summarizes current financial status by collecting information; preparing balance sheet, profit and loss statement, and other reports.
- Substantiates financial transactions by auditing documents.
- Maintains accounting controls by preparing and recommending policies and procedures.
- Guides accounting clerical staff by coordinating activities and answering questions.
- Reconciles financial discrepancies by collecting and analyzing account information.
- Secures financial information by completing data base backups.
- Maintains financial security by following internal controls.
- Prepares payments by verifying documentation, and requesting disbursements.
- Answers accounting procedure questions by researching and interpreting accounting policy and regulations.

- Complies with federal, state, and local financial legal requirements by studying existing and new legislation, enforcing adherence to requirements, and advising management on needed actions.
- Prepares special financial reports by collecting, analyzing, and summarizing account information and trends.
- Maintains customer confidence and protects operations by keeping financial information confidential.
- Maintains professional and technical knowledge by attending educational workshops; reviewing professional publications; establishing personal networks; participating in professional societies.
- Accomplishes the result by performing the duty.
- Contributes to team effort by accomplishing related results as needed.

7- Financial management

- A financial manager is responsible for providing financial guidance and support to clients and colleagues so they can make sound business decisions.
- As a financial manager, you will need a good head for figures and for dealing with complex modelling and analysis, as well as a sound grasp of financial systems and procedures.
- Clear budgetary planning is essential for both the short and long term, and companies need to know the financial implications of any decision before proceeding.
- In addition, care must be taken to ensure that financial practices are in line with all statutory legislation and regulations.
- Financial managers may also be known as financial analysts or business analysts.

8- Mechanical Engineers Description

Perform engineering duties in planning and designing tools, engines, machines, and other mechanically functioning equipment. Oversee installation, operation, maintenance, and repair of such equipment as centralized heat, gas, water, and steam systems.

9- Operator

A production operator, also known as a machine operator, uses equipment to assist with manufacturing, packaging, and other steps along a production line. While the exact duties may vary from company to company, a production operator may be expected to handle heavy machinery such as forklifts. On-the-job training may be available.

6.2 Management Team Gaps

The business strategy for NGCO is to start with a minimum of overhead expenses. As a result, founders will have to cover many of the day-to-day functions that would ordinarily be handled by other staff members. This will cause potential constraints on her time, time that would be better spent on business development and public relations.

6.3 Organizational Structure

Management Structure Figure 1.0

7.0 Financial Plan

7.1 Important Assumptions

Table: General Assumptions

The table below presents some assumptions used in the financial calculations of this business plan.

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7.3 Break-Even Analysis

Table: Break-Even Analysis

Information	Plan A
Price	\$ 1.8
Variable cost	\$ 0.72
Fixed Cost	\$ 4,427
Invested capital	\$ 380,117
Tax rate	25%

Information	Plan B
Price	\$ 3.0
Variable cost	\$ 1.20
Fixed Cost	\$ 6,924
Invested capi	\$ 380,117
Tax rate	25%

Plan A							
Production	Units Sold	Dollar Sales (Revenue)	Fixed Cost	Operating Cost (Total Expense)	Operating Profit (EBIT)	EBIT (1 - T)	ROIC
Terrible	-	\$ -	\$ 4,427	\$ 4,427	\$ -4,427	\$ -3,320	-0.70%
Poor	10,000	\$ 18,000	\$ 4,427	\$ 11,627	\$ 6,373	\$ 4,780	1.01%
Normal	20,000	\$ 36,000	\$ 4,427	\$ 18,827	\$ 17,173	\$ 12,880	2.71%
Good	30,000	\$ 54,000	\$ 4,427	\$ 26,027	\$ 27,973	\$ 20,980	4.42%
Wonderful	40,000	\$ 72,000	\$ 4,427	\$ 33,227	\$ 38,773	\$ 29,080	6.12%
Expected Value	100000	\$ 180,000	\$ 22,134	\$ 94,134	\$ 85,866	\$ 64,399	13.55%
Total of units production estimate per Quarter							

Plan B							
Production	Units Sold	Dollar Sales (Revenue)	Fixed Cost	Operating Cost (Total Expense)	Operating Profit (EBIT)	EBIT (1 - T)	ROIC
Terrible	-	\$ -	\$ 6,924	\$ 6,924.11	\$ -6,924	\$ -5,193	-1.09%
Poor	10,000	\$ 30,000	\$ 6,924	\$ 18,924.11	\$ 11,076	\$ 8,307	1.75%
Normal	20,000	\$ 60,000	\$ 6,924	\$ 30,924.11	\$ 29,076	\$ 21,807	4.59%
Good	30,000	\$ 90,000	\$ 6,924	\$ 42,924.11	\$ 47,076	\$ 35,307	7.43%
Wonderful	40,000	\$ 120,000	\$ 6,924	\$ 54,924.11	\$ 65,076	\$ 48,807	10.27%
Expected Value	100000	\$ 300,000	\$ 34,621	\$ 154,621	\$ 145,379	\$ 109,035	22.95%
Total of units production estimate per Quarter							

Chart: Break-Even Analysis

7.1 Projected Financial Statement

Table: Initial Investment

Details	
CPAEX	
Capital	\$ 200,000
Machine 1	\$ 50,000
Machines 2	\$ 20,000
Deposit	\$ 55,000
Building	\$ 10,000
2 cars	\$ 20,000
Equipments	\$ 10,000
Stores	\$ 1,000
Financial system	\$ 3,000
<i>Total Copex</i>	\$ 369,000
OPAX	
Insurance	\$ 117
Depreation	\$ 1,333
Rent	\$ 1,000
Supervisor salaries	\$ 1,333
Sales salaries	
Office salaries	\$ 2,667
Advertising expense	\$ 167
Delivery expenses	\$ 333
Total expense	
Instalt fees	\$ 667
Hosting include Fotal, Food, Transportation	\$ 333
Traing worker	\$ 500
Rent land	\$ 2,667
<i>Total Opex</i>	\$ 11,117
Total Capital Requirements	\$ 380,117

Table: WACC

Dept	W_d	80.00%
Rate of Dept	r_d	2.50%
Tax (1-T)	0.75	75.00%
Equity	w_c	20.00%
Rate of Equity	r_s	10.00%
WACC		3.50%

Table: Cost of Goods Sold

Cost of goods manufactured

Working in Process 1/1		\$	-
Direct Materials			
Raw Materials Inventory 1/1	\$	-	
Raw Materials Purchases	\$	330,328	
Total Raw Materials available for used	\$	330,328	
Less: Raw Materials Inventory 13/12	\$	16,112	
Direct Materials used		\$	346,440
Direct labor		\$	46,486
Manufacturing overhead			
Indirect labor	\$	4,800	
Factory utilities	\$	4,831	
Factory machinery rent	\$	12,000	
Factory manager's salary	\$	48,000	
Depreciation, Factory Building	\$	25,000	
Indirect materials	\$	3,200	
Insurance, factory	\$	1,404	
Property taxes, factory building	\$	6,000	
Total manufacturing overhead		\$	105,235
Total manufacturing costs		\$	498,161
Total cost of work in process		\$	498,161
Less: working in process, 31/12		\$	-
Cost of goods manufactured		\$	498,161

Cost of goods sold

Cost of goods Sold			
Finished goods inventory, Jan 1		\$	-
Cost of goods manufactured		\$	498,161
Cost of goods available for sale		\$	498,161
Less: Finished goods inventory, Dec 31			
Cost of goods Sold			\$ 498,161

Table: Master Budget

Operation Budget

Master Budget

For the year ending 2019

Sales Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Expected unit sales Product (A) 2.3g	78,261	86,087	94,696	104,165	363,209
Selling price	\$ 1.8	\$ 1.8	\$ 1.8	\$ 1.8	
Total Sales	\$ 140,870	\$ 154,957	\$ 170,452	\$ 187,497	\$ 653,776
Expected unit sales Product (B) 4.6g	39,130	43,043	47,348	52,083	181,604
Selling price	\$ 3.0	\$ 3.0	\$ 3.0	\$ 3.0	
Total Sales (A3)	\$ 117,391	\$ 129,130	\$ 142,043	\$ 156,248	\$ 544,813
Total Sales	\$ 258,261	\$ 284,087	\$ 312,496	\$ 343,745	\$ 1,198,589

Production Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Expected unit sales Product (A) 2.3g	78,261	86,087	94,696	104,165	363,209
Expected unit sales Product (B) 4.6g	39,130	43,043	47,348	52,083	181,604
Desired ending finished goods inventory 5%	4,304	4,735	5,208	5,682	19,929
Total units required	121,696	133,865	147,252	161,930	564,742
Less: Beginning finished good inventory	3,874	4,304	4,735	5,208	18,121
Required unit production	117,822	129,561	142,517	156,721	546,621

Direct Materials Budget Product : A

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Required unit production	117,822	129,561	142,517	156,721	546,621
Raw materials waste (Paper"80%") per unit	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	
Total (Kilo) needed for production	216,792	238,392	262,231	288,367	1,005,782
Desired ending raw materials inventory	11,920	13,112	14,418	50,289	89,739
Total (Tons) required	228,712	251,504	276,650	338,656	1,095,521
Less: Beginning raw materials inventory	10,728	11,920	13,112	14,418	50,177
Raw materials purchases	217,984	239,584	263,538	324,238	1,045,344
Cost per (Kilo)	\$ 0.30	\$ 0.30	\$ 0.30	\$ 0.30	
Total cost of raw materials purchases	\$ 65,395	\$ 71,875	\$ 79,061	\$ 97,271	\$ 313,603

Direct Materials Budget Product : B

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Required unit production	117,822	129,561	142,517	156,721	546,621
Raw materials (Wood"3%") per unit (Tons)	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.03	0
Total (Kilo) needed for production	3,535	3,887	4,276	4,702	16,399
Desired ending raw materials inventory	777	855	940	1,026	3,598
Total pounds required	4,312	4,742	5,216	5,727	19,997
Less: Beginning raw materials inventory	700	777	855	940	3,272
Raw materials purchases	3,612	3,965	4,361	4,787	16,725
Cost per pound	\$ 1	\$ 1	\$ 1	\$ 1	
Total cost of raw materials purchases	\$ 3,612	\$ 3,965	\$ 4,361	\$ 4,787	\$ 16,725
Total cost of raw materials purchases product (A)	\$ 65,395	\$ 71,875	\$ 79,061	\$ 97,271	\$ 313,603
Total cost of raw materials purchases for ALL	\$ 69,008	\$ 75,840	\$ 83,422	\$ 102,058	\$ 330,328

Direct Labor Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Units to be produced	117,391	129,130	142,043	156,248	
Direct labor hours per unit	293.00	293.00	293.00	293.00	
Total direct labor hours required	401	441	485	533	
Direct labor cost per hour	\$ 25.00	\$ 25.00	\$ 25.00	\$ 25.00	
Total direct labor cost	\$ 10,016	\$ 11,018	\$ 12,120	\$ 13,332	\$ 46,486

Manufacturing Overhead Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Variable Costs					
Indirect Labor	\$ 1,200	\$ 1,200	\$ 1,200	\$ 1,200	\$ 4,800
Indirect Materials	\$ 800	\$ 800	\$ 800	\$ 800	\$ 3,200
Utilities	\$ 900	\$ 1,080	\$ 1,296	\$ 1,555	\$ 4,831
Maintenance	\$ 600	\$ 600	\$ 600	\$ 600	\$ 2,400
Other Overhead	\$ 500	\$ 500	\$ 500	\$ 500	\$ 2,000
Total variable costs	4,000	4,180	4,396	4,655	17,231
Fixed Costs					
Supervisor Salaries	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000	16,000
Rent	3,000	3,000	3,000	3,000	12,000
Depreciation	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000	16,000
Insurance	351	351	351	351	1,404
Total fixed costs	11,351	11,351	11,351	11,351	45,404
Total manufacturing overhead	\$ 15,351	\$ 15,531	\$ 15,747	\$ 16,006	\$ 62,635

Selling and Administrative Expense Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Variable Expenses					
Sales Commissions	\$ 1,291	\$ 1,420	\$ 1,562	\$ 1,719	\$ 5,993
Delivery Expenses	1,000	1,100	1,210	1,331	4,641
Total variable expenses	\$ 2,291	\$ 2,520	\$ 2,772	\$ 3,050	\$ 10,634
Fixed Expenses					
Sales salaries					
Office salaries	8,000	8,000	8,000	8,000	32,000
Advertising expense	500	500	500	500	2,000
Depreciation expense	4,000	4,000	4,000	4,000	16,000
Insurance	-	-	-	-	-
Rent	-	-	-	-	-
Total fixed expenses	\$ 12,500	\$ 12,500	\$ 12,500	\$ 12,500	\$ 50,000
Total selling and administrative expenses	\$ 14,791	\$ 15,020	\$ 15,272	\$ 15,550	\$ 60,634

Budgeted Income Statement

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Sales	\$ 258,261	\$ 284,087	\$ 312,496	\$ 343,745	\$ 1,198,589
Cost of goods sold	124,540	136,994	150,694	165,763	\$ 498,161
Gross profit	133,721	147,093	161,802	177,982	\$ 700,428
Selling and administrative expenses	14,791	15,020	15,272	15,550	\$ 60,634
Income from operations					\$ -
Interest expense	16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000	\$ 64,000
Income before income tax	-	-	-	-	\$ -
Income tax expense	33,430	36,773	40,450	44,496	\$ 155,149
Net income / (loss)	\$ 118,929	\$ 132,072	\$ 146,529	\$ 162,432	\$ 420,644

Financial Budget

Master Budget

For the year ending 2019

Schedule of Expected Cash Collections

Sales	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	
Accounts receivable, 12/31/18	-				
First quarter	258,261	206,609			206,609
Second quarter	284,087	-	\$ 278,922		278,922
Third quarter	312,496	-	\$ -	\$ 306,814	306,814
Fourth quarter	343,745	-	\$ -	\$ -	\$ 337,495
Total collections	1,198,589	\$ 206,609	\$ 278,922	\$ 306,814	\$ 337,495
					\$ 1,129,840

Schedule of Expected Cash Payments for Direct Materials

Purchases	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	
Accounts payable, 12/31/18	69,008	\$ 20,702			20,702
First quarter	75,840	-	\$ 71,057	\$ -	\$ -
Second quarter	83,422	-	-	\$ 78,114	\$ -
Third quarter	102,058	-	\$ -	-	\$ 89,013
Fourth quarter	-	-	\$ -	\$ -	\$ -
Total payments	330,328	\$ 20,702	\$ 71,057	\$ 78,114	\$ 89,013
					\$ 258,887

Cash Budget

	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4
Beginning cash balance	\$ 10,000	\$ 107,442	\$ 268,955	\$ 449,208
Add: Receipts				
Collections from suppliers	206,609	278,922	306,814	337,495
Sale of securities	-	-	-	-
Total receipts	216,609	386,364	575,769	786,703
Total cash available	216,609	386,364	575,769	786,703
Less: Disbursements				
Raw materials	69,008	75,840	83,422	102,058
Direct labor	10,016	11,018	12,120	13,332
Manufacturing overhead	15,351	15,531	15,747	16,006
Selling and administrative expenses	14,791	15,020	15,272	15,550
Equipment purchases	-	-	-	-
Interest	-	-	-	-
Dividends	-	-	-	-
Total disbursements	109,166	117,409	126,561	146,946
Ending Cash Balance	107,442	268,955	449,208	639,757

Table: Cash Flow

Free Cash Flow

Cash Flow Year	CF0 0	CF1 1	CF2 2	CF3 3	CF4 4	CF5 5
Total revenue	-300,000	1,979,851	2,276,828	2,618,352	3,011,105	3,462,771
Cost of Goods Sold		1,361,591	1,565,830	1,800,705	2,070,810	2,381,432
Gross profit		618,259	710,998	817,648	940,295	1,081,339
Selling, general and administrative expenses		64,540	74,221	85,354	98,158	112,881
Earnings before interest, taxes, depr. & amort. (EBITDA)		553,719	636,777	732,293	842,137	968,458
Depreciation and amortization		16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000
Subtract Development Expenditures & Expansion Business		27,686	31,839	36,615	42,107	48,423
Earnings before Interest and taxes (EBIT)		510,033	588,938	679,679	784,030	920,035
Taxes		102,007	117,788	135,936	156,806	184,007
Net Operating Profit After-Tax (NOPAT)		408,026	471,150	543,743	627,224	736,028
Add : back depreciation and amortization		16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000
Free Cash Flow	-300,000	424,026	487,150	559,743	643,224	736,028

Chart: Cash Flow

Income Statement

Budgeted Income Statement					
	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	Year
Sales	\$ 258,261	\$ 284,087	\$ 312,496	\$ 343,745	\$ 1,198,589
Cost of goods sold	124,540	136,994	150,694	165,763	\$ 498,161
Gross profit	133,721	147,093	161,802	177,982	\$ 700,428
Selling and administrative expenses	14,791	15,020	15,272	15,550	\$ 60,634
Income from operations					\$ -
Interest expense	16,000	16,000	16,000	16,000	\$ 64,000
Income before income tax	-	-	-	-	\$ -
Income tax expense	33,430	36,773	40,450	44,496	\$ 155,149
Net income / (loss)	\$ 118,929	\$ 132,072	\$ 146,529	\$ 162,432	\$ 420,644

Chart: Balance Sheet

Budgeted Balance Sheet	
December 31, 2018	
Assets	
Cash	\$ 639,757
Accounts Receivable	68,749
Finished goods inventory	86,982
Direct materials inventory	16,112
Investments	-
Other Assets & Equipment	369,000
Less: Accumulated depreciation	32,000
Total assets	\$ 1,148,601
Liabilities and Equity	
Liabilities	
Accounts payable	\$ 71,441
Notes payable	64,000
Taxes Payable	155,149
Expenses Payable	68,366
Equity	
Capital	\$ 369,000
Retained earnings	420,644
Total liabilities and stockholders' equity	\$ 1,148,601

Table: Projected Evaluation

Project Evaluation	
WACC	3.50%
NPV	\$ 2,563,932
IRR	140.4%
MIRR	55.86%
Payback	0.96